

The Emotional Spectrum Analysis 16 EEG system: practical and conceptual considerations for objectively investigating experienced emotion in design research

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Abstract

The contemporary reorientation of design research interest away from cognitive transparency in product interfaces towards the imbueing of designed artefacts with emotion-eliciting qualities has precipitated a surge of interest in means of assessing emotionally objectively. A number of methodologies have been proposed that provide a framework for participants' emotional expression (e.g. Kansei rating scales, PrEmo cards). However, these methods are of limited use in more interactive scenarios. Physiological assessment of emotion via tools developed in psychology and neuroscience potentially represent non-invasive means of assessing participants' emotional state without requiring their active reflection. Using as a vehicle for discussion the Emotional Spectrum Analysis system developed by BFL, Kawasaki, Japan, we discuss the contemporary neuroscientific conception of emotion, and the difficulties of adapting research techniques and equipment from academic science to the applied arena of design research, particularly the low intensity of emotion experiences in design research tasks and the difficulties of categorising emotion. We conclude that while such techniques show promise, they are currently underdeveloped, and we draw attention to the potential over-emphasis in the field toward objective assessment of a superficial elicitation of emotional experience, for example by seeing or using a product, at the expense of pursuing a deeper understanding of how people interact emotionally with designed artefacts at the level of personal narrative.

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1. Introduction

The emotional experience an individual derives from contact with an artefact, place or person has historically been characterised as unavailable for dissection, either because it is inaccessible to introspection or because it is inarticulable – at any rate, it is unquantifiable (Coyne, 1999). This view stems predominantly from the difficulty of assessing an individual's subjective experience, in the first instance, and relating that assessment to the highly complex web of reflexively-linked factors which could account for it, in the second.

The contemporary reorientation in design research away from questions of how to achieve cognitive transparency in product use (e.g., Norman, 1988; see Dunne, 1999) towards the imbueing of designed artefacts with qualities that evoke emotion is precipitated by several factors. Undoubtedly, many writers and designers feel the tensions and dissatisfactions so evident in Western(ised) culture can be at least in part attributed to mass industry's historical lack of interest in more emotional, spiritual dimensions to the use of artefacts and environments (see Patzlar & Kurtgözü, 2002, Coyne, 1999, for criticism of the Romantic view of the role of emotional experience in design). More prosaically, the ability to evoke emotion may grant competitive advantage through product innovation and differentiation. The surge of interest within corporations in investigating emotional aspects of design from an objective, quantifying perspective can be seen to largely have derived from the accounting and marketing cultures with which design co-exists in commercial environments (Michlewski, 2006).

In this paper, we discuss objective approaches to the study of emotion that are suitable for application in design research. We deal particularly with using measures of neural activity to assess emotional experience. The application of technology of this type to design research is a new field; we use as a test case the Emotional Spectrum Analysis 16 (henceforth ESA-16) software system for electro-encephalographic (EEG) data analysis to help delineate for the reader problems with this approach as well as its potential benefits.

2. Contemporary Conceptions of Emotion

Even the most casual introspection reveals our emotional state to be complex and difficult to articulate. This richness of affect, whereby subjectively experienced emotion can be ambivalent or even paradoxical, has often been characterised as being a consequence of the blending, mixing or layering of a core set of emotions. The existence of emotions as discrete entities, as expressed in notions of there being a given number of “basic” or “primary” emotions, or an assertion of the existence of an “emotional consciousness” existing independently of conscious, declarative, “rational” thought, has been rendered somewhat archaic by advances in psychology, particularly neuroscience. From the contemporary scientific perspective, emotion is considered an individual’s cognitive representation of their physiological state. Thinking and feeling are, at a physiological level, aspects of a single process occurring in the nervous system, itself a palimpsest of ancestral elements that are highly parallel and reflexively linked (Damasio, 1994). In the Damasian model, a *somatic marker mechanism* exists that ‘ties’ physiological state to perceptual input to create significance, rather than there being a separation between emotional and rational thinking. Some commentators have observed that designers have yet to come fully to terms with these ideas (e.g. Love, 2005), a fact of especial salience when discussing the role of emotion experience in design.

The contemporary neuroscientific conception of the nature and function of emotion does not render inappropriate the use of descriptors of common emotional states, like anger or happiness, as used in everyday contexts. It suggests, rather, that these “pure” states exist as prototypical episodes of emotion, that themselves can be configured as points around the perimeter of an *emotional space* (Russell & Feldman Barrett, 1999). While some researchers consider this space to be adequately described (or only describable) using a single dimension of physiological arousal, the evidence suggests that a monodimensional model does not adequately describe some observed physiological phenomena in emotions as they relate to subjective experience, such as heart rate variability (Rainville, Bechara, Naqvi & Damasio, 2005), and a plausible case has been made for the necessity of a

second dimension of pleasantness of the subjective emotion (Feldman Barrett and Russell, 1999).

3. Assessing Emotion Objectively

Decomposing our subjectively-experienced emotion into a verbal description outside of a prototypical emotional episode is very difficult. The principle quality that must be possessed by an effective methodology of objective emotion assessment is that it must somehow overcome the vagaries of research participants' descriptions of their emotional state, which can be seen as unreliable for a number of reasons. Firstly, verbal self-report relies on participants' assessment and labelling of their emotional state, but provides no way for researchers to judge the accuracy with which they do so (e.g., Turkkan, 2000). Assuming accurate self-reporting, post-hoc categorisation of participants' experiences is problematic and must rely on the subjective judgment of the researchers. A related issue is the social relationship extant between researcher and participant, especially when participants are required to indicate their experience of a designed artefact that they may associate with the labours of the (present and enquiring) researcher. In such a situation participants are likely to minimise negative comment and overstate positive aspects of the experience. (The social aspects of the environment within which such tests are conducted has been comprehensively dissected by sociologists of science; see Latour (1987), amongst others).

Two methodologies that bring some objectivity to this process do so by providing frameworks which can be used to categorise participants' emotional experiences. PrEmo techniques (Desmet, 2002, 2003) capitalise on the universality of external expressions of emotion: smiles, frowns, laughing and crying have been observed to be the same in all cultures (see, e.g., Ekman, 1972). PrEmo methods provide a framework by which research participants can indicate an emotion experienced by referring to an image of its expression, rather than being required to articulate it themselves (Desmet, 2003). It uses a set of fourteen emotions, selected from 347 emotions rated by twenty participants on the dimensions of pleasantness and arousal, after Feldman Barrett and Russell (e.g., 1999;

see below for an exegesis and analysis of their ideas). The selected emotions were those giving the widest spread around this two-dimensional emotional space (the consequential risk of over- or under-emphasis of the included emotions is acknowledged by Desmet, 2003). In the PrEmo system, each emotion is conveyed using an image or animation of an anthropoid form, which communicates the emotion using facial and bodily gestures. By choosing one or more of these images, participants can indicate emotional responses in such a way that they are already allocated to a standardising scheme by the time they are given to the researcher.

Kansei (a.k.a. “affective”) engineering posits an alternative approach to overcoming the nebulosity of verbal language in emotional description. Participants are asked to rate an artefact or image on numerous scales, each scale denoting a range between a subjective, experiential term or a subjectively-judged term (e.g. “happiness”, “fast”) and its antonym (“sadness”, “slow”). The list of terms is usually culled from cultural sources (magazines, the Internet, et cetera) by the research team, and often hundreds are given to participants (Schütte, 2005). The scale-rating data can be analysed to reveal statistically distinct underlying factors across participants (e.g. via exploratory principle components analysis). For example, a significant cluster of terms denoting security might emerge in the assessment of a vehicle interior. This represents the (relatively) objective imposition of frameworks on both how the subjects are able to verbally explain their experience, and on the categorisation of that data by researchers.

4. Physiological Traces of Experience

A comprehensive critique of the aforementioned methodologies is beyond the scope of this paper, but a limitation shared by them is their applicability only in situations where the participants are required to interact relatively little with the artefact or environment serving as test material. To use them in concert with more immersive experiences, such as interaction with an electronic device or virtual environment, is difficult. Describing an experience after the fact is not usually preferable, on the grounds that subtleties will be lost, but encouraging the active documentation of experience by participants in an

ongoing interaction scenario presents its own problems: it necessitates a division of the participant's attention between the principle task and the verbal task of reflecting and commenting on their experience. The more immersed are subjects in the experience, the poorer the quality of commentary that can be expected; the higher the quality of commentary, the less the participant can be said to be immersed themselves in the experience.

However, the technological and methodological development which has yielded the contemporary neuroscientific understanding of emotion outlined above has also provided potential tools and concepts that could plausibly be applied in such research scenarios. Techniques developed within academic science appeal to the design research community because they are derived as they are from professions in which objectivity is considered the apical concern in research. These methods, at least in principle, can provide objective assessment of participants' emotional experience, without requiring active reflection by the participant in the documentation of that experience.

This paper will take as a test case the ESA-16 analysis system for EEG data as an example of a technologically-based emotion assessment methodology. We do not single out this particular system because of its particular virtues or lack thereof, but simply wish to use it as a platform for discussion of the practicalities of the field. To this end, we have provided commendation, explanation and caveat where we feel them applicable.

4.1 Nature and Use of the ESA-16

The ESA-16 system was developed and is manufactured by the Brain Functions Laboratory, Inc., based in Kawasaki, Japan. This system, at present uncommon in the West but proving popular in Japan (Musha, 2005), was designed to objectively categorise the emotion that a wearer experiences. It is designed for use in conjunction with a standard EEG system (ten to fourteen channels, plus electrocardiogram and electro-oculogram inputs). EEG involves the use of electrodes placed on the scalp to record electric activity in the brain, and is a long established, if relatively basic, neuroimaging

method. In order to be effective as a tool for the assessment of emotion, researchers must be able to use a piece of equipment to map out participant emotion in a coherent way. While galvanic skin response, skin conductivity and heart rate can all, with varying accuracy, be used to document levels of somatic arousal, EEG is potentially more versatile in documenting physiological state changes related to subjective experience by providing information about neural activity in areas known to be involved in the functioning of specific emotions (Harmon-Jones, 2003; see discussion below). EEG has greater suitability for many design research studies than other neuroimaging techniques (e.g. functional magnetic resonance imaging), being both much less restrictive of the participant's movement (indeed, portable EEG systems are available) and much simpler to operate. EEG systems are also extremely affordable relative to other neuroimaging systems.

Our discussion of using such technology for objective emotion assessment with the ESA-16 as a representative example largely concerns two areas: the intensity (and reliability) of elicited emotion, and how it is to be related to subjective experience, from a neuro-physiological perspective.

4.2 Elicitation of Emotion

The development of a physiologically-based emotional analysis methodology must be based on a battery of data, usually from a test group whose experience of a set of emotions has been recorded with the relevant equipment. This allows recordings typical of specific states to be identified. An important issue this raises is the intensity of emotional experience that can be expected in a controlled setting. The reliable elicitation of emotion is extremely difficult, not simply because of the heterogeneity of emotional experience, but also because of ethical considerations concerning the invocation of emotion (e.g., how do researchers inspire genuine fear in order to record its physiological affects?). In the case of the ESA-16, seven people “well trained in psychological imaging” (Musha et al., 1997, Musha, 2005) were connected to the appropriate equipment, and asked to “imagine” emotions from a list (Musha, 2005).

The lack of detail both as concerns the nature of the imaging task and how the developers prevented a physiological “overspill” from one evoked emotion to another are reasons for caution. Rainville, et al. (2005), faced with a similar development problem, utilised a considerably larger participant population (n = 43), all of whom had stated on first contact that they could “vividly remember one or two autobiographical episodes where they experienced a strong emotion of fear, anger, sadness or happiness.” (Rainville, et al., 2005, p. 3). Each participant was only required to provide data for one or two emotions, plus a neutral condition, usually by recalling a mundane task such as doing laundry.

Irrespective of the developmental method, it should be noted that the problem of low intensity of elicited emotion follows the equipment to its role within design research. One of the most difficult reconciliations to be made in emotion-based design research is the paucity of intensity of emotional experience derived from contact with conventional products and environments, as has been acknowledged by Desmet (2002, 2003). The methods described above that to a greater or lesser extent enforce a framework for emotional expression onto participants (e.g. Kansei rating scales, PrEmo) avoid one of the key problems in this line of design research, which is the inconsequentiality of most emotional experience involved in the use of artefacts, environments et cetera. They share the virtue of forced-choice paradigms in being able to detect small effects. The case is more complicated with physiologically-based methods of emotion assessment like the ESA-16, which must be sensitive to minor changes in physiological state. Eliciting sufficient physiological activity within a design research task may prove difficult.

4.3 Categorisation of Emotion from Neural Activity

The development process of the ESA-16 system required the identification of patterns of neural activity typical to emotional states from the original battery of participants. The nature of patterns of neural activation in emotional experience remains, as of writing, a highly contentious area. Neural correlates of emotion are widely distributed, and include the activation of areas that play an important role in other cognitive functions (Prohovnik, et al., 2004); it is clear from the extant literature that there is no simple way to map neural

activity onto emotion. Rather than seeking discrete foci of neural activation typical to specific emotions, BFL identified four patterns of activity that were, as near as was possible, orthogonally rotated (i.e. completely independent of and dissimilar to one another)(Musha, et al., 1997, Musha, 2005). In English translation, these patterns corresponded to the elicited states of ‘joy’, ‘sadness’, ‘relaxation’, and ‘anger’ (later renamed ‘stress’ by the BFL team). We assume these terms do not have connotations identical to the original Japanese terms from which they are translated; the naming scheme may be amended in future versions of the system (Musha, 2005). Selection of these states because they correspond to highly dissimilar patterns of activation is very much a pragmatic, rather than conceptually led, development choice. But without a clear way to map neural activity to a range of specific states as yet (Russell & Feldman Barrett, 1999) there would seem to be little current alternative if specific states rather than general neural trends are sought.

These four distinct patterns of activity were codified into the analytical structure of the ESA-16 software. In use, the software indicates the relative ‘levels’ of these four states of the wearer as collated every 5.12 seconds – i.e., how closely the wearer’s neural activity accords to each of these four spatial configurations. As the selection criteria for these states was the near-orthogonal relationship they display, multiple states may be simultaneously evident, such as ‘relaxation’ concomitant with ‘anger’/’stress’. It is difficult to conceive of a situation in which these two states could be complementary (assuming the English equivalents of the original terms connote correctly), and while there are similarities, this four-dimensional model of emotion does not sit well with two-dimensional emotional spaces (see Feldman Barrett & Russell, 1999, for discussion of evidence pertaining to simultaneous experience of contradictory emotions).

As the ‘levels’ of each emotion are based on goodness-of-fit to a predetermined spatial configuration of neural activity, they can be seen as being on an arbitrary scale for each participant, not allowing for direct comparison of emotional intensity across participants for the same stimulus. Furthermore, the very small size of the sample group raises doubts about the detection of individual differences, both in brain morphology and in style of

emotional experience, and it remains possible that the sample was unrepresentative of the wider population. Wider participation and cross-cultural testing would seem to be the only way to correct this (Musha, 2005).

5. Conclusion and Discussion of General Issues

The ESA-16 is a good example of the current state of affairs when advances in the neuroscience of emotion are transferred out of the theoretical and into the applied arena. While such measures have clear promise, and there is a definite case for non-invasive means of objectively assessing emotional experience without requiring active allocation of attentional resources by research participants, especially in interaction design, there is a considerable distance yet to be covered before sufficient reliability can be demonstrated with technologies of this type for them to become a practicable option in most design research contexts.

All of the objective techniques discussed above, including the PrEmo and Kansei, share a general issue in their application. This relates to the distinction between *causes* and *objects* of emotion. Design researchers must be aware that the object of emotion and the cause of an emotion are not necessarily the same – the cause of an emotion is an eliciting event (Goldie & Doering, KCL) like *seeing* or *buying* a product; the object of emotion is not necessarily present or indeed tangible – it may be, for example, a perceived status or social role. Insofar as products are *emotional*, they are elicitors for emotion, reliant on a substrate that is better expressed in terms of personal narrative than by physiological examination. From this perspective, it appears unrealistic that physiological measures of emotional state can supplant more conventional user testing techniques, but may complement them usefully; they are more suited to validation (i.e. showing that the desired emotion was experienced) than explanation (why this was so).

In the short term, we would like to suggest a repurposing of these technologies away from research into *emotion* and toward the documentation of *immersion*. The authors

consider that the principle issue with use of the ESA-16, as an example, neither relates to the size of the physiological data battery used in its development, nor the means of acquisition of said data, both of which can be addressed in future phases of development; the principle issue is rather that, in order to convince as a research tool, equipment to assess emotional state from physiological measures must provide data that fits into a coherent and empirically-validated model of emotion. At present, such a thing does not exist, although the conceptual foundations do, in the shape of two-dimensional models of the structure of affect. Before a compelling model of subjectively experienced emotion that is linked to physiological data comes into existence, we consider that the utility of methods such as EEG to non-invasively document arousal with greater subtlety than (for example) cardiac measures can be put to advantage in a different way. Especially in immersive environments, such as when playing computer games or functioning in other highly interactive situations, there is a strong case to assess the patterns of arousal over time, that is to say, the levels to which the participants engage and disengage while in the immersive environment. This constitutes a considerably simpler task than seeking to position an individual's emotional experience at a point in multi-dimensional emotional space at a given moment. It is our view that in the short term the limitation of ambition in the arena is advisable. A decomposition of the concept of emotion, via a decoupling of the dimensions of emotional space, has the potential to be of greater utility in design research contexts than do notions of design for the emotions as they are conventionally conceived.

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